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The Homoerotics and Monstrous Otherness of *Teen Wolf*

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In the telenarrative series *Teen Wolf* (2011–) male characters negotiate hegemonic and counter-hegemonic masculinity and in turn sexual identity. Scott McCall, played by Tyler Posey, is a “normal” teenaged boy who is bitten by a werewolf and who subsequently must adapt to the changes that his new identity requires; he simultaneously learns about a plethora of supernatural threats that endanger his friend, family and community. The 6 season, 80 episode *MTV* series is punctuated with a number of frequently shirtless, muscular young men whose relationships are often complicated by an undercurrent of (and in at least two cases, explicit) homoeroticism. Scott’s close friend Stiles Stilinski (Dylan O’Brien), werewolf Alpha Derek Hale (Tyler Hoechlin), High School jock and werewolf Jackson Whittemore (Colton Haynes), twin brothers and werewolf pack members openly gay Ethan and heterosexual Aiden (Max & Charlie Carver) and openly gay Danny Mahealani (Keahu Kahuanui) are all involved in a wide variety of highly emotional (and occasionally sexual) relationships complemented with intricate displays of affection and loyalty, love and lust, anger and aggression. This article maps and interrogates the homoerotically dynamic and changing male relationships between these characters amidst the larger conceptual background of monstrosity that renders same sex desire visible in ways that invite both heterosexual (and possibly sexual minority) audiences and viewers into illusory, utopic constructions of sexual diversity and egalitarianism divorced from the reality of contemporary America’s “tolerance trap”. Suzanna Danuta Walters defines the concept of the “tolerance trap” in her book of the same name as our collective willingness to “...settle for a watered-down goal of tolerance and acceptance rather than a robust claim to comprehensive civil rights” (Walters).

Teen Wolf is a science fiction/horror teen drama appearing on the *MTV* network which is loosely related to the 1985 *Teen Wolf* film. The television series revolves around the life of Scott McCall (played by Tyler Posey), a white, heterosexual, middle class high school sophomore who resides in Beacon Hills — itself a primarily white, heterosexual community in a utopic middle America. The series premiered on June 5, 2012 and has consistently been renewed by *MTV* for over 5 seasons and for a total of 80, 40 minute episodes. As recently as June 5th, 2016 the showrunner Jeff Davis confirmed that the series would be renewed for another season, its sixth, with continued potential for renewal. In

terms of plot the series revolves around McCall and a close coterie of friends who must struggle with an increasingly diverse array of supernatural phenomena subsequent to Scott’s being bitten and infected with lycanthropy. Scott’s best friend Stiles Stilinski (human) played by Dylan O’Brien along with Derek Hale (Werewolf) played by Tyler Hoechlin, lacrosse antagonist Jackson Whittemore (human) played by Colton Haynes and Liam Dunbar (werewolf) played by Dylan Sprayberry are instrumental to his ability to cope with the ensuing changes in his life; they also help him in his defense against innumerable supernatural obstacles the discovery of which coincide with Scott’s developing lycanthropy. For the purposes of this article, my attention will be directed to the hegemonic male homophilous relationships on the series, though other scholars have, and will undoubtedly, examine equally compelling homoerotic female relationships. Although the circumstances and events over the course of 5 seasons complexify their relationships, at the beginning of their introduction, these are the primary, presumably heterosexual male characters of the series many of whom continue to appear repeatedly over the past 5 seasons. Posey appears from S01 – S06; O’Brien from S01 – S06; Hoechlin appears from S01-S04; Whittemore from S01- S02.

In terms of critical reception, the series has earned a number of awards over the course of its 5 season stretch (Fig. 1), indicating a sustained interest in the lives and characters who appear on *Teen Wolf* with its target demographic, who overwhelmingly are comprised of teens and young adults between the ages of 12 - 34 (Ng). Indeed, at its premier the series was first in its time slot among teens in this age bracket and, according to Jeff Davis, the series significant online viewership was a contributing factor to the network’s decision to renew *Teen Wolf* for its sixth season (Gorman). Over the past five years, the series has consistently maintained a weighted average of approximately 1.61 million viewers per season. This is especially significant for the age demographic when one considers that people aged 24 and under watch “roughly two fewer hours of live TV...per week. And 25 to 34 year olds (roughly speaking, millennials) watch an hour less per week, down from 27 and a half hours to 26 and a half hours.” About “50 percent of Americans now have subscription services like Netflix, Amazon Prime, and Hulu in their homes” (Koblin) which is up from 42 percent in 2015. Young adults familiar with technology generally use streaming devices like, tablets, laptops and phones to watch their media content. Consequently, their consumption numbers are systematically underestimated since Nielsen metrics rarely account for these non-TV devices. However, Gorman notes that “Tablets are now in 58 percent of American homes...and time spent consuming media on tablets has increased 63 percent from 2014” (Gorman). Thus this demographic

of viewer is an untapped share of the consumer base for series like *Teen Wolf* actively promoted on streaming networks like MTV and Netflix.

In terms of the composition of the cast, only a few individuals explicitly identify as a sexual minority. Danny Mahealani, played by Keahu Kahuanui is a Hawaiian, openly gay student and a human at Scott's high school. He is also a fellow lacrosse team player; Ethan (werewolf), played by Charlie Carver, is a white, openly gay lacrosse team player and member of Scott's pack who briefly dates Danny in Season 3; Mason Hewitt (human) played by Khylin Rhambo is an openly gay African American student at Scott's school and ultimately becomes enmeshed in a supernatural predicament of his own (more on this later) and briefly dates Lucas (chimera) played by Eddie Ramos; Brett Talbot (werewolf) played by Cody Saintgnue is a bisexual lacrosse team player for Devenford Prep, an opposing school, but quickly becomes involved with many of Scott's friends and pack members; And finally, Corey (a chimera, the result of an experiment by the Dread Doctors that produces a werewolf type creature with none of the supernatural vulnerabilities or characteristics other werewolves possess) played by Michael Johnston, is a student at Scott's high school and very recently returned from the dead with a renewed love interest in Mason Hewitt. What's most striking about this composition of characters is that they are overwhelmingly white, middle to upper class and almost without exception, openly gay or bisexual. Beacon Hills is a community that hosts its own mixed gay club *Sinema*, where under-aged teens can go to dance and mingle, and many of these characters are or have at one point been involved in same sex relationships.

These factors set the series far above many other telenarratives on contemporary American television, even within the sci-fi/horror genres where sexual nonconformity is more frequently introduced. Significantly, Scott McCall has had only two girlfriends over the course of the series and Jeff Davis has indicated that he will be single for the final season of the series stating "Does Scott always need to have romance in his life to be a compelling character?" He also indicated, "We thought this might be a season where we don't see that side...this season sees Scott as a single guy trying to graduate and be there for his friends" (Highfill) which might also betray a strategic capitulation to the heavy and persistent online interest in the "bromance"(Becker) between Scott and his best friend Stiles. Ultimately the setting and characters created by Davis and his production team are a reflection of an idealized queer utopia in Middle American Beacon Hills; the setting functions as a glaring contrast to the reality of the LGBTQ community in the real world of America 2016. We can infer much about this counter-hegemonic positioning with a more detailed analysis of

the characters and their lives on *Teen Wolf* in the following pages where I hope to elaborate on precisely what kinds of messages are being communicated, to whom and for what purposes. Subsequent to this introduction is a discussion about my methodology and a brief description of the theory of narrativity upon which dramatic scripted series like *Teen Wolf* are premised. In addition to an in depth textual analysis of the characters previously mentioned, I critically interrogate how the ubiquitous genre conventions of "monstrosity" functions within the narrative to communicate discrete messages about sexual hegemony and nonconformity.

Methodology

The author watched all 5 seasons and 80 episodes, constituting approximately 53 hours over the course of 30 days at roughly 2 episodes per day (occasionally varying rates depending upon schedule). These episodes were initially watched in 1080p resolution by streaming delivery through Amazon Prime. These episodes were subsequently downloaded and electronically stored for later retrieval for review. The author then used VLS Media Player for retrieving those episodes and reviewed their content at both normal and 1/2 frame rate speeds for close examination. Although the series is commercially available for minimal costs in 2-disc DVD formats on a Season basis, given their low resolution and reduced detail, the author opted to digital copies in lieu of physical media (also in keeping with the primary format by which its target demographic regularly consumes its content). The author took handwritten notes while watching the series, periodically pausing to record his observations without breaks until the completion of each episode. These notes comprised the bulk of the analysis conducted for this publication and found in later sections. In consultation with extant sources, the author systematically evaluated each episode plot, season by season, for content germane to the search for the character's appearances, and their actions and dialogue were recorded and transcribed for use in this work. As the author, I utilized textual analysis as a qualitative methodology to focus on the discursive forces present in a text as an important means of understanding how individuals and society constitute themselves and make sense of the larger world in which they live. Research shows that textual analysis can usefully interrogate how mass mediated commodities create identities and "construct authoritative truths"(Saukko) for those who use (or are represented as using) them, thereby illuminating the participatory (or non-participatory) role social actors possess in the creation, reflection and consumption of those truths. The multiple interpretations of a given "text" construed broadly, frequently look different when examined in relation

to other texts or social sensibilities; thus the task of analysis is not to ascertain the most "correct" interpretation but rather to explore some of the possible and undiscovered interpretations embedded in the targets of textual analysis.

I utilize textual analysis to examine the method by which this telenarrative "text" gains and retains social value over time (in the form of explicit messages about heterosexuality and homoeroticism) through its conspicuous consumption by its primarily young adult audience. The strength of textual analysis lies in its ability to expose the (1) discourses through which texts communicate their message, (2) the sociopolitical contexts by which those messages are situated or mediated, and the (3) lived experiences these messages attempt to represent or replicate. While attempting to get to the "truth" of a particular target, textual analysis facilitates multiple, multidimensional, nuanced, and tentative ways of understanding while frequently employing deconstructive techniques which expose the "historicity, political investments, omissions and blind spots" (Saukko) of social truths which are understood as possessing their own continuously contested, but often tightly regulated possibilities. For these purposes, I employ the use of textual analysis in this investigation to bring to light the complexities of homoeroticism as it is manifested in this series and the variety of social meanings we might infer from those examples as embodied in a small segment of series characters.

Television Narratives

Teen Wolf is first and foremost a television show, before anything else. And because of this, one must be familiar with the theory of television series and their conventions. For the purpose of this research, I refer interchangeably to both "television series" or "shows" and "telenarratives" to mean the same thing, with the obvious caveat that, regardless of vocabulary, television functions through a process of narration. Telenarratives are important areas of intellectual inquiry as they serve as the vehicle through which meaning is constructed, disseminated and interpreted by their viewers. The process of narration reflects on one level, the way in which information is offered, withheld, or delayed in order for viewers to cognitively process that information in ways that resonate with them in order to construct and interpret meaning. Additionally, at another level narratives possess broader socio-cultural, political, and ideological components.

The combination of two factors: surface level narrativity (the process of narration) and the broader components of the narratives' texts, illustrates the dynamic way in which narratives combine to create a comprehensive whole. Narratives have finite and obvious beginning and endings and communicate continuities and change. Narratives are linked through 'a chain of events in

cause-effect relationship occurring in time and space' that is premised upon a storyteller and receiver model which serves as a principle way in which knowledge about the world is communicated (Gillespie 82). The privileging of one viewpoint (from a relationship with a given historical time for example) over another viewpoint (from more recent historical era) influences how narratives operate for televisual viewers. Indeed, Marie Gillespie notes 'knowing what and whose stories get told or remain untold is crucial to understanding the exercise of power in society. Stories about events and characters, real or fictional, may be shaped in way that serve the interests of powerful institutions such as governments or business' (83).

Corporate networks like *MTV* are well aware of how a viewer's need to be entertained functions as a discrete attraction to telenarratives as the vehicle by which these concepts are materialized. Specifically, a viewer's desire for entertainment (or epistemophilia), is essentially a "desire to know." Indeed, many viewers manifest this epistemophilia through an attraction to "their" characters. Committed viewers are interested in what happens to the characters-how they develop relationships, how they cope with various obstacles week after week, and season after season. Viewers tend to feel similar to characters who are like themselves in terms of demographic characteristics such as gender, race and age. Hoffner and Buchana argue that 'some degree of similarity to media characters seems to promote a desire to be like them, possibly because certain similarities signal that it is both possible and appropriate for the viewer to become like the character in additional ways' (328).

The viewers who regularly watch *Teen Wolf* often self-identify as 'subcultural viewers' as they 'watch TV in order to participate in niche communities both online and offline...viewers participate in subcultural communities because of an affinity for particular content'(Seles 19). Indeed, examining favorite characters is a common method of investigating audience reactions to media portrayals and responses to favorite characters are informative because of their significance for viewers (Hoffner and Buchana 337). According to the 'drench hypothesis' even one salient role model who exhibits appealing traits can have a strong impact on audience members who are drawn to that character (Greenberg). Thus recurring characters have enormous potential to affect the attitudes, values and behaviors of the audience (Papa). This is particularly true given that the overwhelming majority of *Teen Wolf's* protagonists are young, white, conventionally masculine men, with muscular bodies and classical good looks who physically embody the epitome of hegemonic masculinity in contemporary America. It is through that process of selection that audiences thereby express affinity for and adopt the 'meanings,

pleasures and social identities' promulgated for their consumption, often times originating from characters (and the actors who portray them) who look, act, speak, believe, and behave nothing like them. Fiske makes clear that characters are not simply reflective, non-productive facsimiles, but rather operate as "metonymic representations of social positions and the values embedded in them"(158). Indeed, the subset of characters examined here dress like a typical cross section of white, straight middle America almost as a caricature of those identity categories by faithfully reproducing the hegemonic cultural icons which appeal to the series' target demographic. This is equally true for gay males whose gay masculinity is racialized as white even in cases where the character's ethnicity is not (Connell; Fejes).

Although Danny is phenotypically Hawaiian and Mason is African American, their performances on the series reproduce a racially homogenized gay masculinity that is safely read as hegemonically white. The non-threatening consequences for this ensure viewer fidelity through their racial palatability and acceptability as identifiable gay characters on the series. Their presence as gay men of color is rendered invisible amidst the many other white gay males with whom they appear and for whom they are the only objects of affection or potential relationships. Although Mason does seek out Latino Lucas at Sinema for what appears to be a sexual tryst, the consequences of this attempt result in him being attacked by Lucas has involuntarily been transformed into a monster. Thus the pedagogical purpose of this appears to be that white gayness remains the primary gay identity to which all others must subscribe in order to maintain the veneer of diversity without threatening the racial status quo for the viewing audience's target demographic.

Given the fandom for the series in online fora, one could easily conclude that at least some of *Teen Wolf's* viewership are significantly attached to one or more of its characters in a type of parasocial relationship. Baker-White law concludes that "Getting fandom to love you is easy, because fans want to interact with the actors, writers, and creators behind their favorite media. The hard part is retaining that love once you have it"(Baker-Whitelaw). This dependency on fan fidelity reflects an equal kind of dependency and dedication by fans to their favorite characters that is well recognized in communication and fandom scholarship alike. Johnathan Cohen and others argue that "television characters (both real and fictional) offer their viewers an opportunity to do more than simply watch; they offer simulated interaction...Indicators of such relationships are similar to attributes of personal relationships: feeling sorry for the characters when they make a mistake, missing them when they are gone, looking forward to seeing them, wishing to meet them in person, and asking information about

them"(Cohen; Rubin, Perse and Powerll).

This is particularly important for multi-season series over time because the "longer the viewer has been involved in a parasocial relationship with a character, the higher the level of confidence in the attribution of the character's behavior"(Perse and Rubin) and in the case of *Teen Wolf*, the high involvement of the fan base as reflected in various conventions illustrates a heavy investment in the lives of the series characters, especially those who have survived year after year. While it may be easy to dismiss such research, one is advised by Cohen that we often have relationships with people who are real, but whose relationships are imaginary. His persuasive example is that "political leaders are very real, as are the consequences of their actions, we know them only through the media. In terms of our feelings toward them, the quality of the interaction we have with them, or their reality in our lives, they're probably more similar to a television or movie star, than to a family member or co-worker"(Cohen).

Reflecting on the impact of the media on his decision to come out, Charlie Carver, who plays Ethan, notes that "I feel more and more people, particularly young people, are striving to create a safe world for each other...I now believe that by omitting this part of myself from the record, I am complicit in perpetuating the suffering, fear and shame cast upon so many in the world" (Carver). But he was not the only one to cite the contradictory nature of playing straight in the real world while playing gay on television. Indeed, Colton Haynes who played Jackson Whittemore for two seasons belatedly revealed his queer sexuality amidst a plethora of media attention given his visibility as an ostensibly heterosexual character on *Teen Wolf* and the apparent duplicity between his public and private lives (Snetiker).

Conditional Inclusivity and Gay Utopias

Many of the characters appear amidst a plethora of ostensibly heterosexual characters in the Beacon Hills community. Like students in many contemporary American high schools, the young people of Beacon Hills look, sound and generally act much like their peers on *Teen Wolf*. They often wear the same kinds of clothes, they use the same vernacular and behave similar to what one would find in a similarly generic, white, middle class community. The setting of the series is therefore an important departure point for examining how our characters deviate from the hegemonic norms mimicked in the series. Notably, the presence of gay men is remarkably well tolerated – if not embraced – by the heterosexual youth at Beacon Hills high school. Despite the plethora of reports of bullying and discrimination targeting young gay men across America's high schools of 2016, these problems are all but eradicated in the fictional world of *Teen Wolf*. Indeed,

if the term “utopic” or “utopia” is best described as “an imaginary place in which the government, laws, and social conditions are perfect” (Merriam-Webster), then there’s no better place for gay and bisexual men than in Beacon Hills. Indeed, much of the critical acclaim directed to the series is explicitly because of its utopic depictions of queer normalcy perpetrated in a type of egalitarian paternalism directed by its heterosexual characters at the sexual minorities on the series. In a type of self-congratulatory acknowledgment of this state of affairs, some of the actors have made important observations in this regard. Tyler Posey noted that “I think it’s perfect and natural, and I think the kids that watch the show really do respect the way we include gay characters. That’s why Charlie and Keahu – the characters they play are so popular. We love it and we’re happy to be able to show kids that it’s OK to be who you are”(Peeples).

Of course the dilemma with this statement is that Tyler must mean that Ethan’s death almost immediately after he falls in love with Danny, and Danny’s three season celibacy and the death of his only lover are what’s “perfect and normal.” This is despite Scott’s ability to have not one but two serious heterosexual relationships. One wonders if these are the conditional terms by which inclusivity is defined on the series by Season three. Being gay or bisexual apparently also means being willing to be quietly deprived of a normal and fulfilling relationship on one’s own terms. Interestingly Tyler Hoechlin (who plays Derek Hale) observed that he loved “the freedom that we’ve had with MTV and Jeff Davis has done a great job of keeping that [LGBTQ presence] a central part of the show. It’s an important thing that the demographic that’s watching the show is being introduced to that and is able to see it”(Peeples). Despite Hoechlin’s departure after the fourth Season, his assertion about the network’s oversight and the Executive Producer’s influence about casting decisions and story arcs reflects an important kind of surveillance in the kinds of ways that sexual minorities appear and are presented to the series target audience of young adults and teens.

Although Dylan O’Brien (who plays Stiles Stilinski) argues that the utopic absence of homophobia in an American high school setting “sets a good example”(Peeples) one wonders for whom that example is made? It would appear that it sets a satisfying example of social progressivism for many in heterosexual society by fulfilling their need to feel egalitarian, but it potentially creates a palpable danger of perpetrating a flawed sense that homophobia is a social anachronism despite all the data accrued in social sciences to the contrary. According to Baker-Whitelaw, “When the show began in 2011, showrunner Jeff Davis said that if he could write a story about werewolves, then he could set it in a world without sexism, racism, or homophobia. And he got off to a good start...

there are several secondary gay or bisexual characters who are treated without a hint of homophobia by the main cast”; however, by the third season Danny is still alone (not for trying) and the only openly gay character. Thus, by the third season *Teen Wolf* has “apparently transitioned into a show where white men receive dynamic storylines and everyone else shuts up or dies, fans were not pleased”(Baker-Whitelaw). An analysis of the characters germane to this research reveals the following data:

Gay/Bi Characters	Season(s)	Episodes	Current Status
Danny Mahcalani (human)	S01 – S03	27	Lover Died (Ethan); Single again
Ethan (werewolf)	S02 – S03	19	Single; His? twin brother is dead
Mason Hewitt (human)	S04 – S06	42	Attacked by potential date (Lucas); Single: unwillingly turned into a Beast
Lucas (chimera)	S03	1	Dead
Brett Talbot (werewolf)	S04 – S05	16	Bisexual, but asexual
Corey (chimera)	S05 – S06	29	Lover died (Lucas); killed and resurrected; Badly burned; Literally becomes invisible
<i>Average</i>		22.3	
Straight Characters	Season(s)	Episodes	Current Status
Scott McCall (werewolf)	S01 – S06	101	2 girlfriends later, single
Dylan O’Brien (human)	S01 – S06	101	Dating
Derek Hale (werewolf)	S01 – S04	61	Disappeared
Jackson Whittimore (werewolf)	S01 – S02	25	Formerly dated Lydia Martin; Dead
Liam Dunbar (werewolf)	S04 – S06	48	Dating Hayden Romero
<i>Average</i>		62.7	

(Figure 1)

As we can see in fig.1, the data reveal a number of interesting facts. Not only do the gay or bisexual characters in the series have the 1/3 airtime than their ostensibly heterosexual counterparts at 22.3 episodes versus 62.7, their ultimate fates over the course of their appearances are dramatically different. Although Jackson Whittimore is dead, one (Lucas) is also dead while another (Corey) has been killed, resurrected, badly burned and literally turns invisible to viewers. In fact, his attempted relationship with Mason Hewitt is itself not particularly stable when examined against the longevity of Scott, Liam or Jackson’s relationships. Moreover, Danny, Ethan, and Brett are all single at the time of this article’s initial drafting. But equally and no less depressing is the fact that lovers in the gay/bi group appear to die quite quickly with both Lucas (lover to both Corey AND Mason) dying while Ethan’s twin is also killed rendering him brotherless, and Lucas and Danny are alone again.

Qualitatively the differences are striking in terms of how gay/bi sexuality is treated on *Teen Wolf*, especially in comparison to heteronormative relationship

trajectories. The conditions under which gay/bi characters appear on the series thus necessitate that they be single; have brief, asexual or limited physical relationships; kiss privately or engage in limited public displays of affection; and have their lovers die or attack them before dying (while they themselves are attacked, involuntarily turned into literal monsters or made to become invisible). While the supernatural characteristics of the series explain some of these events, but our analysis must account for some of these circumstances despite the conventions of the genre, if we are to arrive at a full and complete picture of the representation of gay individuals in this television show. As Avila-Saavedra makes clear, "media criticism requires going beyond issues of numeric representation of gays and lesbians towards an analysis of the nature and complexity of such representations in the context of a broader notion of hegemony"(8).

Samantha Henderson calls *Teen Wolf* a "homoerotic gay masterpiece" alluding to the series' early "homoeroticism and gratuitous shirtlessness" and the vanilla make out scene between Danny and Ethan in a motel. She also argues that "...the show is important because it insists on representing gay characters positively and without mockery" and despite the abject tokenism of Danny's solitude as the gay character for the first three seasons, she concludes that "I have continued to be pleasantly surprised by the decidedly nonchalant incorporation of gay characters"(Henderson). Henderson's superficial review notwithstanding, the incorporation of these characters into the series reflects a measured approach of limited inclusivity and incrementalism that purports to create the appearance of equality and egalitarianism towards sexual diversity. But beneath the surface, monstrosity and gay sexuality walk hand in hand on a path of marginalization, demonization and ruthless heteronormativity. Avila-Saavedra argues that the "presence of homosexual characters in American television would seem to imply an endorsement of a liberal agenda of tolerance and inclusion of alternative lifestyles and sexual orientations"(5) and undoubtedly Jeff Davis and MTV have desperately attempted to communicate that appearance on *Teen Wolf*. But these appearances come with a cost that, according to Dow "...does not always translate into social tolerance or recognition, particularly because the fictional media narratives tend to emphasize the interpersonal issues of homosexuality and avoid political ones" (Dow) and this is true in the case of *Teen Wolf* as well.

There is no activism for sexual minorities in *Teen Wolf*, as the setting was strategically made in a queer utopia where such distracting political messages are unnecessary. "Despite the increased visibility of gay and lesbian people in contemporary society (presaged by popular cultural exemplars in the media), that visibility is near universally characterized by whiteness, youth and hegemonic

maleness" (Johnson Jr., "Race, Aging and Gay In/Visibility on US Television"). As David Eng makes clear this process of inclusion has occurred within the context of an historical trend: "gays and lesbians were once decidedly excluded from the normative structures of family and kinship, [and] today are re-inhabiting them in growing numbers and in increasingly public and visible ways...Our current moment is marked by the merging of an increasingly visible and mass-mediated queer consumer lifestyle..."(Eng). Johnson notes that "the path to this historical and political moment has been paved by corporations' sensitivities to their customer's diverse tastes in palatable, but socially-appearing advancements in modern sensibilities about discourses of 'tolerance' and 'diversity' when applied to sexual minorities. Modalities of 'tolerance' have become prominent as domesticated norms of integration and assimilation in ways that capitalize upon a presumptively universal virtue..."(Johnson Jr.). Thus the popularity of *Teen Wolf* is in many ways directly attributable to the efficacy of domesticating depictions of same sex desire embodied in characters like Aiden, Danny, Mason, Brett, etc. that reinscribes the normality of that sexual difference by its heterosexual characters (Derek, Scott, Jason, etc.) without any tangible evidence of actual engagement beyond mere recognition.

Sarah Schulman makes clear, that this process of commodification has larger, more extensive sociocultural meaning. She states that the "breadth of ideas (about sexuality) permitted into the popular discourse is extremely narrow" and those ideas are always accompanied by a rhetoric of "diversity" in which "tolerance" becomes an "intrinsic component of how dominant- culture people feel about themselves, how they rationalize their privileges and justify their own sense of objectivity. Today we face a 'tolerance' defined by the diminishment of the minority and the heroization of the majority, a 'tolerance' that simply acknowledges that the minority exists and that claims acknowledgment as an act of generosity"(Schulman). Because American society values youth so highly and because youthfulness has become an indispensable component of hegemonic masculinity, some gay people (and I dare say certain characters) are at risk of being perceived by society as even less masculine. Robinson makes clear that "nowhere in contemporary Western society is this emphasis on youthfulness more pronounced than in the gay world"(Robinson).

"Stromos", Bromances and Supernatural Homoeroticism

The series plot repeatedly defines the masculinity of its gay male characters conditioned upon the acceptance of *Teen Wolf's* heterosexual male characters; gay masculinity is recognized as a type of masculinity only because straight male characters acknowledge its legibility. Scott, Derek, Jackson are all instrumental

in acknowledging and tacitly accepting the masculinity identities of the sexual minorities in the series. Indeed, according to Avila-Saavedra, "the heterosexual man's masculinity is never threatened or affected by the proximity of gay men; rather it is reinforced by servitude" (15). Any homoerotic pairings that might arise on the series are not inherently threatening so long as the heteronormative foundation of the ostensibly straight characters is convincingly maintained. According to Baker-Whitelaw last summer, *Teen Wolf's* PR team, "...earned themselves a lot of positive fandom karma by releasing a video of two of the lead actors cuddling on a boat. The video was a reference to the popular fanfic... of Stiles and Derek (Sterek), and fans were overjoyed to see a male/male pairing being acknowledged by the show's creators...The...video was a direct appeal to fans who wanted Stiles and Derek to get together for real, arguably the largest and most vocal contingent of the show's fan base" (Baker-Whitelaw). Although there is a vocal fan following of the Sterek phenomena who wish to see Stiles and Derek together, the executive production staff have consistently denied all attempts to see those desires fulfilled. That decision is a reflection of two things: First the "bromance" between Stiles and Scott appears to be perceived as more than adequate by the network for fans to see this desire fulfilled and second, that heterosexuality's stability remains an indispensable component of the narrative story world. It is not surprising that the series "bromance" is limited to only *one* pair of men who also coincidentally just happen to be the *primary* protagonists of the series. Equally significant to the series' "bromance" are the genre conventions of science fiction and horror which subtend and define how homoeroticism appears on screen. The supernaturalism of *Teen Wolf's* landscape fills the series with especially fertile ground upon which deviations in sexual desire can appear. When freed from the boundaries of the "normal" non-supernatural world, a wide array of sexualities is rendered both feasible and possible (Greven; Johnson Jr.).The presence of what Peter Redman calls the "monstrous Others" is intrinsically central to the narrative's logical operation; and second, the conventions of the genre operate within the parameters established by that logic in some fundamental ways without which, the series otherwise could not function. Redman argues that:

Critical commentary on the genre tends to stress that the horror story is fundamentally concerned with the instability of identity, the threat of boundary invasion and boundary dissolution...the horror story can be read as replaying this constant failure of conscious identities. The loss or breakdown of boundaries which is central to the genre parallels the endless disruption of identity (107-108).

According to Johnson, "this narrative setting, is itself an element whose cultural meaning predictably reproduces a social hierarchy of [sexual] Others (both supernatural and human), thereby making those very Others who are the most threatening, simultaneously desirable" ("Discourses" 160). This fact is reproduced with characters like Aiden, Danny, Mason, Brett, etc. who all occupy this position of sexual monstrosity within the *Teen Wolf* narrative because their same sex desire poses the most threat to the heterosexual dominance of the series. Redman further observes that "sexuality or 'sexual energy' is one of the crucial factors that is heavily policed in contemporary culture and which returns to consciousness in the horror genre" (Redman 109-110).

Thus it should be no surprise that the series creator and network executives have carefully constructed a story world that takes advantage of Redman and Johnson's observations but mitigates the advantages of appearing to be sexually egalitarian against the financial (and sociopolitical) disadvantages of actual enfranchisement by obfuscating same sex desire within the conventions of supernaturalism in the horror genre. And so sexual minorities become mere plot devices that become "value added" components to an otherwise conventional werewolf narrative.

Conclusion

This research has attempted to critically interrogate the frequency and conditions under which gay male characters appear within one popular cultural television series as a means to assess how same sex desire is itself communicated to American society. It does not, nor does it necessarily intend to assess how those messages are consumed by the audiences to whom it is broadcasted. Here I make the case that the conditional inclusivity of these characters reveals an important component of how same sex desire tentatively appears to be adopted by one major network corporation in a single award winning, multi-season series. This will not be the end of any discussion about how sexual difference deviates in discrete ways from a hegemonic heterosexual norm; I dare say that is a discussion that will continue within the scholarship for some time to come. However, I believe that analyses such as this, series by series, can yield impressive results in the aggregate, when conducted rigorously with attention to the cultural and socioeconomic conditions of their production, the messages they communicate and the people for whom and from whom these narratives originate. I argue that even in circumstances that superficially appear to be atypically welcoming, and indeed utopic (as is the case with *Teen Wolf* here), an undercurrent of barely disguised marginality remains its most defining feature.

In many ways *Teen Wolf* reproduces some of the same features of early television productions which were characterized by an unwillingness to depict same sex desire and gay men as worthy of full emancipation in their sexual lives. A primary difference from those early gay characters to today is that the palpable fear of seeing them on screen is no longer a barrier to their enfranchisement, but rather the most defining feature of their identity – their sexuality – remains intransigently obfuscated or tokenized into submission. That these conditions persist, even on a series whose target demographic is one most popularly understood to accept sexual difference as inconsequential, reveals something significant about those in decisions making positions in Hollywood and the risk averse nature of corporate media that consumers of all sexual categories should be attentive to; viewers of utopic representations of sexual diversity on television must therefore remain ever vigilant.

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Youth and the Older Crowd: *The Almighty Johnsons* and Redefining Coming of Age Television

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Coming of age series have populated American television over the last few decades. Shows like *The Wonder Years*, *Gilmore Girls*, and *Buffy the Vampire Slayer* have presented different kinds of teen characters in transition. Usually these series foreground a teenaged male or female protagonist and include the narrative conventions associated with coming of age film or television: "young heterosexuality, frequently with a romance plot; intense age-based peer relationships and conflict either within those relationships or with an older generation...coming-of-age plots focused on motifs like virginity, graduation, and the makeover" (Driscoll, *Teen Film*, 2).

A current New Zealand television fantasy dramedy, *The Almighty Johnsons* (which was broadcast on TV3 in New Zealand from 2011-2013 for three seasons)¹ incorporates some of these common coming of age conventions including young romance, the virginity motif, peer relationships and conflicts with an older generation. The series, co-created by James Griffin and Rachel Lang, enhances the conventions of the *Bildungsroman*² or coming of age narrative by adding the fantasy premise of characters who have alternate identities as gods³ and focuses on a twenty-one year old student, Axl Johnson, who discovers that he is the Norse god Odin. *The Almighty Johnsons* also extends the concept of "coming of age" and the kind of behavior usually associated with "youth" to a variety of age groups including twenty-somethings, and older characters in their 30s and 40s. *The Almighty Johnsons* seems to be responding to some of the social issues affecting Western society including children who are still financially dependent on their parents. It also engages with issues of dependence and independence as they affect older characters who may be stand-ins for baby boomers, and the series reflects the changes in the family structure in New Zealand society from the norm of dual parent families to a greater number of single parent families.⁴ The genre of the fantasy dramedy and ITV3's redefinition of its target audience also facilitate the changing representations of youth, adulthood or coming of age in contemporary television culture and in Western society.

The initial focus of *The Almighty Johnsons* involves the coming of age of Axl Johnson (Emmett Skilton), a young New Zealander who was essentially raised by his older brother Mikkel or Mike (Tim Balme) in the absence of both